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Review Article

HUMAN PAPILOMA VACCINE OVERVIEW

Mohammed Ibrahim Habadi ¹, Hassan Hamdan Nafea Aljohani ², Maryam Abdalhadi Altayeb ³, Hassan Abdullah Alwosibai ⁴, Mazad Ali Salman Allehyani ⁵, Maryam Ahmed Makki Almozaïn ⁶, Abdullah Mana Mohammed Alqahtani ⁷, Ranim Abdulhamid Alrahwan ⁸, Fatimah Ali Awad Alwadei ⁷, Marah Mohammed Alzaidi ⁹, Faisal Saleh Mansi Alharthy ¹⁰, Rami Abdullah ALSuwat ¹⁰, Nawaf Saleh M Alamri ¹⁰

¹Consultant Of Family Medicin, Department of Family & Community Medicine, Jeddah University-Jeddah, Mihabadi@uj.edu.sa, 0505324283, ²PHC Almontazah Alsharqi, ³Batterjee Medical College, ⁴Arabian Gulf University, ⁵Umm Al-Qura University, ⁶Maternity Children's Hospital Dammam, ⁷King Khalid University, ⁸Ibn Sina National College For Medical Studies, ⁹King Faisal Hospital-Taif, ¹⁰King Fahad Air Base –Taif.

Abstract:

Introduction: Human papillomavirus (HPV) linked cancers can affect the cervix, vulva, vagina, penis, anus, rectum and oropharynx. It is estimated that more than eighty percent of all HPV linked cancers arise from the cervix, almost all of the evidence for prophylactic vaccine prevention of incident type specific HPV infection is in cervical disease. The early vaccine to be approved, Gardasil, has been substituted by Gardasil 9 whose overall prevention of CIN 3 disease is not-inferior to that of the competing cervical cancer HPV vaccine, Cervarix.

Aim of work: In this review, we will discuss HPV vaccine

Methodology: We did a systematic search for HPV vaccines using PubMed search engine (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>) and Google Scholar search engine (<https://scholar.google.com>). All relevant studies were retrieved and discussed. We only included full articles.

Conclusions: Prophylactic HPV vaccines are commercially available and part of many high income nations' immunization budgets. While Cervarix remains the most cost effective vaccine with proven efficacy in one dose, theWHO recommends two doses for either Gardasil9 or Cervarix for those up to 15 years of age, and three doses for women 15 years or older. TheWHO recommendations are based on induced antibody titers at month 7 for Gardasil and Gardasil9 as there are currently no efficacy data for these vaccines in fewer than three doses. TheWHO recommendations for Cervarix are based on efficacy data in addition to immunogenicity data. Three dose efficacy preventing CIN 2 or worse by any HPV type is about 62% for both Cervarix and Gardasil9; the three dose efficacy preventing CIN 3 or worse by any HPV type is 93% for Cervarix and 43% for Gardasil, with no data for Gardasil9. All three vaccines lead to reduced numbers of colposcopies and excisional cervical therapies. Head to head trials indicate that Cervarix has superior immunogenicity compared to Gardasil for T-cell and B-cell functions for both HPV 16 and 18; there are no data for Gardasil9's comparable immunogenicity. The immunogenicity data for HPV 18/45 induced by Gardasil and Gardasil9 indicates that long term surveillance for HPV 18/45 disease breakthrough must be in place. Revaccinating females already HPV vaccinated is expensive and causes harm with no evidence of any improved prevention of HPV infections.

Key words: HPV vaccines, importance, composition, cervical cancer.

Corresponding author:

Mohammed Ibrahim Habadi,

Consultant Of Family Medicin, Department of Family & Community Medicine,
Jeddah University-Jeddah, Mihabadi@uj.edu.sa, 0505324283.

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Human papillomavirus (HPV) linked cancers can affect the cervix, vulva, vagina, penis, anus, rectum and oropharynx [1] It is estimated that more than eighty percent of all HPV linked cancers arise from the cervix, almost all of the evidence for prophylactic vaccine prevention of incident type specific HPV infection is in cervical disease [2]. The early vaccine to be approved, Gardasil, has been substituted by Gardasil 9 whose overall prevention of CIN 3 disease is not-inferior to that of the competing cervical cancer HPV vaccine, Cervarix [3].

In this review, we will discuss the most recent evidence regarding

METHODOLOGY:

We did a systematic search for HPV vaccines using PubMed search engine (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>) and Google Scholar search engine (<https://scholar.google.com>). All relevant studies were retrieved and discussed. We only included full articles.

The terms used in the search were: HPV vaccines, importance, composition, cervical cancer.

VACCINE COMPOSITION:

All the 3 vaccines have synthetically manufactured virus like components (VLPs) of the L1 epitope. Gardasil9 has more than 2 times the antigenic load and more than 2 times the aluminum load of Gardasil; Gardasil9 has more concentrations of L1 virus like particles (VLPs) for HPV 16 and 18 to trigger antibody responses that are non-inferior to Gardasil [4]. Cervarix has the slightest antigenic concentration of the three vaccines, and has an advanced adjuvant for improved immunogenicity, AS04. AS04 is similar to a Toll-like receptor 4 agonist providing direct stimulation of antigen presenting cells, marked cellular and humoral immune responses, and long-lasting antibody responses [5].

IMMUNOGENICITY:

Immunogenicity as an endpoint

The World Health Organization (WHO), the National Cancer Institute (NCI), and the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) approved in 2013 that immunologic non-inferiority was a enough endpoint for VLP based HPV vaccine trials for those 16–26 years of age following continuous type-specific infection protection for at least 6 months was established [6]. For younger people younger than 16 years, WHO standards specify that immune bridging studies showed non-inferior antibody titers to those in the 16–26 year old group are the only agreed

endpoint; and, for those older than 26 years, prevention of persistent infection for at least six months with vaccine specific HPV types was satisfactory for declaring prevention at the cervical, anal and oral anatomical sites. Vulvar/vaginal protection must be proven by actual disease prevention defined as grade 2/3 HPV 16/18 specific intraepithelial neoplasia (VaIN 2+/VIN 2+).

Comparison of the immunogenicity of three doses of HPV vaccine

Head to head trials of 3 doses of Cervarix vs Gardasil in women [7] and in 12–15 years old adolescents are done. Seropositivity for anti-HPV16 titers following five years is high for both Cervarix and Gardasil, however the actual induced GMTs measured by pseudovirion based neutralization assay (PBNA) are markedly less for Gardasil than Cervarix; the decline in titers may influence the long term duration of protection. Gardasil has markedly less seropositivity retention and GMTs for anti-HPV18 titers than Cervarix. Cervarix also showed marked higher serum binding antibody responses for both HPV 16/18 than Gardasil. Gardasil9 triggers the same anti-HPV16/18 responses as Gardasil. Similarly, Gardasil is inferior in comparison with Cervarix both in percentage and geometric mean number of CD4+ T cell responders against both HPV16 and 18; as well as the significantly lower geometric mean number of memory B cells for HPV18 at 48 months.

The duration of antibody response is important for clinical prevention of HPV infection. Cervarix has high anti-HPV16 and HPV18 antibody titers for at least nine years [8] in follow-up studies; Gardasil has plateaued anti-HPV16 titers well above natural infection titers for at least nine years, however anti-HPV18 titers that are not different from natural infection titers as early as twenty four months following the vaccination [9].

Gardasil9, in 3 doses, has similar loss of seropositivity and decrease in GMTs for HPV18 as Gardasil had [10]. About twenty percent of Gardasil9 recipients had a loss of detectable anti-HPV18 titers after 24 months. In Gardasil recipients, after one and half years over ten percent of females who had no detectable anti-HPV18 titers, after 3 years over 20% of women lost detectable titers, and after 5 years nearly 35% of women lost detectable titers. About fifteen percent of Gardasil9 recipients had a loss of detectable anti-HPV45 titers after 24 months.

Booster doses after a three dose Gardasil series

The pre-adolescent females vaccinated with 3 doses of Gardasil have no marked antibodies to other

oncogenic HPV types than HPV16/18. With Gardasil9 replacing Gardasil, there is a temptation to re-vaccinate these young girls for the purpose of preventing five more oncogenic HPV types. A trial checked this hypothesis [11] giving 3 doses of Gardasil9 one to three years after the initial three doses of Gardasil compared to giving three doses of Gardasil9 de novo. GMTs calculated at peak (one month after the third dose) revealed that among the females already vaccinated with Gardasil, there was an anamnestic response for HPV 16/18 with titers two to three fold higher than among the girls vaccinated de novowith Gardasil9. Though, the revaccinated females had markedly lower anti-HPV31/33/ 45/52/58 titers than among the females getting Gardasil9 for the first time.

Immunogenicity of fewer than three doses

Cost studies have reliably specified that if 3 doses of prophylactic HPV vaccine do not provide protection from type-specific HPV infection for at least fifteen years, cervical cancer will only be postponed, not prevented [12]. Compliance with 3 dose schedules is challenging, but, particularly in underserved areas and developing countries. Balancing the opportunity for fewer than 3 doses with the antibody mediated long term protection is now necessary.

Both Cervarix and Gardasil trigger similar antibody titers in 2 doses as in 3 doses, for their respective vaccine, if the two doses are six months apart. (Cervarix) and 2 (Gardasil) reveal anti- HPV16 and HPV18 titers for vaccination schedules of fewer than three doses [13].

Decreasing the time to 1 month, instead of 6 for Cervarix triggers a lower peak titer, however a plateau level at 48 months that continues to be above the natural infection titer level, and only little bit below plateaus of 3 doses and two doses at 6 month intervals. Likewise, a shorter interval of two months for the Gardasil second dose triggers a lower peak titer than any other dosing scheme.

Whereas 2 doses within three months is not recommended, the similar plateau GMTS by 36 months indicate that titers are enough above natural infection titers and mirror the plateaus of the longer 2 dose interval and three dose schedules; the only question becomes the duration for which the short interval two dose antibodies are maintained.

Increasing the time interval to 1 year following the initial Gardasil dose for girls 11–13 years leads to 12 month plateau titers for anti-HPV16 and HPV18 that are equivalent to the plateaus maintained for a three

dose Gardasil schedule [14]. Giving 2 yearly interval doses can increase compliance; a 3rd dose at month 24 may increase longevity of antibody duration. Protection during the vaccination process has not been assessed. Single dose schemes have also been examined. One dose of Cervarix induces significant antibody titers for both HPV16 and 18 that are above natural infection titers by 9 and almost 5 fold, respectively.

Immunogenicity in women older than 25 years

Both Gardasil and Cervarix were tried in women 25–45 years old (mid-adult) using 3 doses. Peak antibody titers for anti-HPV16 among mid-adult Gardasil recipients are non-inferior to those induced in 16–26 year old young females. Similarly, 4 month follow-up plateaus are similar for both age groups. Retention of seropositivity for anti-HPV16 remains above 97% for both mid-adult and younger women over time. By contrast, though, Gardasil induced anti- HPV18 titers in mid-adult females are markedly lower at peak than in younger females and drop to non-protective natural infection titer levels by twenty four months.

Cervarix, triggers at least a fifty fold higher peak titer than natural infection for both anti-HPV16 and HPV18 among females older than 25 years, similar to the response in 16–25 year old women. Plateau titer levels following 6 years continue to be non-inferior to the younger women for anti-HPV16 titers in the mid adult women; and, while anti-HPV18 titers are below the plateau of 16–25 year olds by six years in mid adult women, they remain substantially above natural infection titers. All mid adult women retained seropositivity for anti- HPV16 at six years ,with 97% retention for anti-HPV18. At 10 years after vaccination, 96% of women expressed anti-HPV16 seropositivity and eighty five percent of females expressed anti-HPV18 seropositivity [15].

EFFICACY:

Efficacy, as described by prevention of persistent type specific HPV infection, has been shown for those females who are seronegative and PCR DNA negative for each vaccine relevant HPV type. Other variations within this population involve the number of vaccine doses, baseline cytology, whether females were negative for all 14 oncogenic HPV types at baseline, and whether new cases of infection or disease were considered from the first day of the study or after the 3rd vaccination. The All women were 15/16–24/ 26 years old, with the majority being 18–24 years. 4.1. Efficacy against incident infection and disease A collection of all vaccine efficacy studies for WHO described endpoints of infection and cervical disease for the 3 vaccines. The efficacies

are studied for the most HPV naïve populations and are showed with 95% confidence intervals.

Among females already HPV DNA vaccine type specific positive at the time of vaccination, none of the vaccines trigger clearance of the infection or disease [16]; these are only prophylactic vaccines.

Prevention against abnormal screening and its sequelae

The subsequent need for diagnostic colposcopies declines proportionally to the screening results. The decrease in excisional therapies, although significantly higher both in proportion and in significance. The cost reductions in diagnostic and therapeutic procedures enabled by HPV vaccination contribute to their societal value.

Efficacy against non-cervical endpoints

Non-cervical disease endpoints were planned for regulatory evidence only for Gardasil and Gardasil9. The WHO vaginal/vulvar endpoints are VaIN 2/3 and VIN 2/3 disease for which Gardasil has efficacies in the per protocol population of 100% (95% CI: 50, 100) and 100% (56, 100), respectively, for those related to HPV 16/18 [39]. Gardasil9 does not have any reported efficacies for this endpoint or a VaIN/VIN 2/3 related to HPV 31, 33, 45, 52, 58 endpoint [40]. The intent to treat population analysis shows infinitely broad 95% confidence intervals around the 100% efficacy for HPV 16 VIN 1 (no worse grade outcome was reported) and 95% confidence intervals of 37 to 97 around the 86% efficacy for HPV 16 related VaIN 1; there was no efficacy for HPV 18 related VIN/VaIN 1 [17]. Gardasil and Gardasil9 did not have anal endpoints for women; and did not include oral HPV 16/18 infection endpoints.

While Cervarix studies did not have regulatory trial data for extracervical sites, the NCI Costa Rica Vaccine Trial group investigated prevention of oral, vulvar and anal persistent HPV 16/18 infection four years after vaccination in an intent to treat population. The HPV vaccine efficacy against vulvar HPV 16/18 infection was 54% (95% CI: 5, 79), and efficacy against oral HPV 16/18 infection was 93% (95% CI: 63, 100) four years after vaccination. In the full analysis approximating the intent to treat population, the efficacy against anal HPV 16/18 infection was 62% (95% CI: 47, 73) four years after vaccination; and efficacy against anal non-vaccine related HPV 31/33/45 infections was 49% (95% CI: 30, 64). HPV 16/18 infections often occurred at both the cervix and anal sites, with vaccine efficacy against HPV 16/18 infection regardless of cervix,

anal or oral site at four years of 71% (95% CI: 63, 78) in the full cohort. These analyses show that Cervarix is protective against HPV 16/18 infection regardless of the anatomic site of infection.

GLOBAL REACTION TO HPV VACCINATION OVER THE PAST DECADE:

From June 2006 when the regulatory approval of the first HPV vaccine occurred, through October 2014, 68 countries and 12 territories adopted a HPV vaccine implementation program [18]. Gardasil9 was not approved until December 2014, hence is not included as a vaccine possibility in this historical review. The WHO two dose schedule was not recommended until late 2014 and is also not reflected in this historic review. Nine high income countries have continued follow-up of the female three dose HPV vaccine series: USA, Australia, England, Scotland, New Zealand, Sweden, Denmark, Canada, and Germany. Seven years of follow-up, 2007–2014, shows a population-level impact after female vaccination when population vaccine coverage rates exceed 50% [60]. The incidence of HPV 16/18 infections decreased by 64% after HPV vaccination program initiation in girls younger than 20 years. The decrease in HPV 16/18 incidence was proportional to the population three dose vaccine coverage rate: the higher the coverage rate, the higher the decrease in HPV 16/18 incidence. In addition, the incidence of HPV 31, 33 and 45 decreased by 28% in the same cohort of girls indicating population evidence of cross protection that was seen in the Cervarix trials. In women 20–24 years old, the incidence of HPV 16/18 decreased by 31% over the same time frame, and was also proportional to the vaccine coverage rate achieved by the catch up vaccination programs in each of the countries (e.g. the greater the proportion of 20–24 year olds who received three HPV doses, the greater the decrease in HPV 16/18). There was a small increase in the non-vaccine high-risk HPV types (RR = 1.09, 95% CI: 0.98–1.22) among the population with the lowest uptake of HPV vaccine among the 20–24 year olds, but no increase among populations with high coverage. Only one study documented a 21% decrease in CIN 2+ lesions seven years after girls 15–19 years old received three doses of HPV vaccine [19].

CONCLUSIONS:

Prophylactic HPV vaccines are commercially available and part of many high income nations' immunization budgets. While Cervarix remains the most cost effective vaccine with proven efficacy in one dose, the WHO recommends two doses for either Gardasil9 or Cervarix for those up to 15 years of age, and three doses for women 15 years or older. The

WHO recommendations are based on induced antibody titers at month 7 for Gardasil and Gardasil9 as there are currently no efficacy data for these vaccines in fewer than three doses. The WHO recommendations for Cervarix are based on efficacy data in addition to immunogenicity data. Three dose efficacy preventing CIN 2 or worse by any HPV type is about 62% for both Cervarix and Gardasil9; the three dose efficacy preventing CIN 3 or worse by any HPV type is 93% for Cervarix and 43% for Gardasil, with no data for Gardasil9. All three vaccines lead to reduced numbers of colposcopies and excisional cervical therapies. Head to head trials indicate that Cervarix has superior immunogenicity compared to Gardasil for T-cell and B-cell functions for both HPV 16 and 18; there are no data for Gardasil9's comparable immunogenicity. The immunogenicity data for HPV 18/45 induced by Gardasil and Gardasil9 indicates that long term surveillance for HPV 18/45 disease breakthrough must be in place. Revaccinating females already HPV vaccinated is expensive and causes harm with no evidence of any improved prevention of HPV infections.

REFERENCES:

1. **How many cancers are linked with HPV each year?** [Internet] Available from www.cdc.gov/cancer/hpv/statistics/cases.htm.
2. **F. Bray, J. Ferlay, M. Laversanne, D.H. Vrester, C. Gombe Mbalawa, Kohler, et al.,** 2015 Cancer incidence in five continents: inclusion criteria highlights from volume X and the global status of cancer registration, *Int. J. Cancer* 137 (2015) 2060–2071.
3. **L.M. Fernandez, M.E. Pendleton, R.B. Wright, D.M. Harper,** Chapter 29 bivalent HPV vaccine approved for cervical cancer prevention in females, in: A. Ayhan, N. Reed, M. Gultekin, P. Dursun (Eds.), *Textbook of Gynaecological Oncology*, third ed. Gunes Publish.
4. **M.H. Einstein, P. Takacs, A. Chatterjee, R.S. Sperling, N. Chakhtoura, M.M. Blatter, et al.,** Comparison of long-term immunogenicity and safety of human papillomavirus (HPV)-16/18 AS04-adjuvanted vaccine and HPV-6/11/16/18 vaccine in healthy women aged 18–.
5. **S.L. Giannini, E. Hanon, P. Moris, M. Van Mechelen, S. Morel, F. Dessy, et al.,** Enhanced humoral and memory B cellular immunity using HPV 1/6/18 L1 VLP vaccine formulated with the MPL/aluminum salt combination (AS04) compared to aluminium salt only, *Vaccin.*
6. IARC HPV Working Group Report, Primary End-points for Prophylactic HPV Vaccine Trials, vol. 7, 2013 (Lyon, France. ISBN 978-92-832-2451-8).
7. **M.H. Einstein, M. Baron, M.J. Levin, A. Chatterjee, B. Fox, S. Scholar, et al.,** Comparison of the immunogenicity of the human papillomavirus (HPV)-16/18 vaccine and the HPV-6/11/16/18 vaccine for oncogenic non-vaccine types HPV-31 and HPV-45 in healthy women.
8. **P.S. Naud, C.M. Roteli-Martins, N.S. De Carvalho, J.C. Teixeira, P.C. de Borba, N. Sanchez, et al.,** Sustained efficacy, immunogenicity, and safety of the HPV-16/18 AS04-adjuvanted vaccine: final analysis of a long-term follow-up study up to 9.4 years post.
9. **M. Nygard, A. Saah, C. Munk, L. Tryggvadottir, E. Enerly, M. Hortlund, et al.,** 2015 Evaluation of the long-term anti-human papillomavirus 6 (HPV6), 11, 16, and 18 immune responses generated by the quadrivalent HPV vaccine, *Clin. Vaccine Immunol.* 22 (8) (2015) .
10. Statistical Review of Gardasil9-[Internet] <http://www.fda.gov/downloads/BiologicsBloodVaccines/Vaccines/ApprovedProducts/UCM428669.pdf>.
11. **S.M. Garland, T.H. Cheung, S. McNeill, L.K. Petersen, J. Romaguera, J. Vazquez-Narvaez, et al.,** 2015 Safety and immunogenicity of a 9-valent HPV vaccine in females 12–26 years of age who previously received the quadrivalent HPV vaccine, *Vaccine* 33 (48) (2015).
12. **R.V. Barnabas, P. Laukkanen, P. Koskela, O. Kontula, M. Lehtinen, G.P. Garnett,** 2006 Epidemiology of HPV 16 and cervical cancer in Finland and the potential impact of vaccination: mathematical modeling analyses, *PLoS Med.* 3 (2006), e138. .
13. **M. Safaeian, C. Porras, Y. Pan, A. Kreimer, J.T. Schiller, P. Gonzalez, et al.,** Durable antibody responses following one dose of the bivalent human papillomavirus L1 viruslike particle vaccine in the Costa Rica Vaccine Trial, *Cancer Prev. Res. (Phila.)* 6 .
14. **K.M. Neuzil, D.G. Canh, V.D. Thiem, A. Janmohamed, V.M. Huong, Y. Tang, et**

- al.,2011 Immunogenicity and reactogenicity of alternative schedules of HPV vaccine in Vietnam: a cluster randomized non-inferiority trial, *JAMA* 305 (14) (2011) 1424–1431.
15. **T.F. Schwarz, A. Galaj, M. Spaczynski, J. Wysocki, A.M. Kaufmann, P.V. Suryakiran, et al.**, Persistence of Immune Response 10 years After Administration of the Human Papillomavirus (HPV) 16/18 AS04-adjuvanted Vaccine to Women Aged 15–55 Years, *European Res.*
 16. **J. Paavonen, P. Naud, J. Salmerón, C.M.Wheeler, S.N. Chow, D. Apter, et al.**, Efficacy of human papillomavirus (HPV)-16/18 AS04-adjuvanted vaccine against cervical infection and precancer caused by oncogenic HPV types (PATRICIA): final analysis of a double.
 17. **FUTURE I/II Study Group, J. Dillner, S.K. Kjaer, C.M. Wheeler, K. Sigurdsson, O.E. Iversen, et al.**, Four year efficacy of prophylactic human papillomavirus quadrivalent vaccine against low grade cervical, vulvar, and vaginal intraepithelial neoplasia and .
 18. **L. Bruni, M. Diaz, L. Barrionuevo-Rosas, R. Herrero, F. Bray, F.X. Bosch, et al.**,2016 Global estimates of human papillomavirus vaccination coverage by region and income level: a pooled analysis, *Lancet Glob. Health* 4 (2016) e453–e463, [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S2468-2667\(16\)30101-1](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S2468-2667(16)30101-1).
 19. **J.M. Brotherton, M. Fridman, C.L. May, G. Chapell, A.M. Saville, D.M. Gertig**,2011 Early effect of the HPV vaccination programme on cervical abnormalities in Victoria, Australia: an ecological study, *Lancet* 377 (9783) (2011) 2085–2092.